

Report on WikiProject International Botanical Congress 2024

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[Siobhan Leachman](#) ([User:Ambrosia10](#)) Wikimedia Aoteaora New Zealand
[Heidi Meudt](#) ([User:Stitchbird2](#)) National Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa
[Sabine von Mering](#) ([User:S.v.Mering](#)) Museum für Naturkunde Berlin, Germany
[Joaquim Santos](#) ([User:Joaquimsantos1978](#)) University of Coimbra, Portugal

[Wikidata WikiProject IBC 2024 contributors at the XX International Botanical Congress](#) by Siobhan Leachman [CC0](#) via Wikimedia Commons

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WikiProject IBC 2024

The Wikidata WikiProject International Botanical Congress 2024 was organised by [Heidi Meudt](#), a Wikimedian and botany curator at the Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa (Te Papa), [Siobhan Leachman](#), a New Zealand Wikimedian, [Sabine von Mering](#), a Wikimedian, botanist and data scientist based at the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin, Germany, and [Joaquim Santos](#), a Wikimedian, biologist and collection manager from the University of Coimbra, Portugal.

Initial idea

The initial idea for this workshop and outreach opportunity came about at the suggestion of Heidi Meudt. She obtained funding from her institution, Te Papa, to attend the [XX International Botanical Congress 2024](#) (IBC 2024). Heidi is based in Wellington, New Zealand and is an active member of the [Wikimedia Wellington meetup](#).

Heidi has been a close collaborator with Siobhan Leachman, the co-organiser of the in person Wikimedia Wellington meetup and the [Aotearoa New Zealand Wikimedia meetup](#), on various Wellington and New Zealand based initiatives. Heidi suggested to Siobhan that they could collaborate on a presentation at IBC 2024 as well as propose a Wikidata workshop to be provided to attendees. Heidi, in her initial email in November 2023, also asked Siobhan if there were any other botanical Wiki colleagues that may be interested in collaborating.

Siobhan immediately included her Wiki colleague Sabine von Mering. Siobhan and Sabine had been collaborating on another Wiki adjacent project, the [Women Genera project](#), of which Sabine was the main organiser. Sabine and other participants with this project had previously discussed both submitting an abstract on the Women Genera project to IBC 2024 and also attendance at IBC 2024. Carmen Ulloa Ulloa, on behalf of the group, submitted an [abstract](#) highlighting this project to the IBC 2024 organising committee.

Another of our collaborators on this Women Genera project, [Sandy Knapp](#) (who was a member of the IBC 2024 Advisory committee, the president of the IBC 2024 Nomenclatural Section and an invited IBC 2024 keynote speaker) was very keen to have members of the group attend the Congress. She encouraged Siobhan to attempt to find funding to attend. However, it was only as a result of Heidi's proposal that Siobhan committed to apply for funding.

At the first meeting between Heidi, Siobhan and Sabine it was decided that we would propose a Wikidata workshop and that Heidi would submit an abstract to the conference organisers on our behalf. At that meeting we also decided we wanted our project to support both English and Spanish speaking botanists to engage with Wikidata. IBC 2024 would be held in Madrid over two weeks in July 2024, so we saw this as an ideal opportunity to grow the Spanish speaking Wikidata community.

We also wanted to encourage attendees from Spanish speaking South American countries. South America is a biodiversity hotspot and we wanted to train botanists from South America to contribute their knowledge to the Wikiverse.

We aimed for our Wikidata workshop participants to work on botanical collectors from both the Iberian Peninsula as well as South America. We therefore invited Joaquim Santos to join our team. Joaquim is the collection manager at the Herbarium of the University of Coimbra in Portugal. This herbarium has an extensive database of botanical collectors who collected in both those areas.

Joaquim had also previously collaborated with both Sabine and Siobhan on other projects including producing the [TDWG data standard for people identifiers](#) which recommended the use of Wikidata Qids in that data standard. Thus relationships established during multiple prior collaborations resulted in this collaboration.

What is the International Botanical Congress?

[IFEMA Madrid Venue for the conference portion of the XX International Botanical Congress](#) by Siobhan Leachman, [CC0](#) via Wikimedia Commons.

The [International Botanical Congress](#) is a meeting of thousands of botanists from all over the world. It happens once every six years, and is the largest and arguably most important botany conference in the world. The International Botanical Congress comprises two important parts and is held over two weeks.

The first part is the [Nomenclature Section](#) where agreement is reached on changes to the [International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi and plants](#). The second part is a botany focused conference comprising keynote lectures, plenaries, oral presentations and posters, and also includes workshops, a conference dinner, and field trips. Our group proposed to present at the conference portion of the Congress on the benefits botanists gain by engaging with the Wikiverse and to offer a botany focused Wikidata workshop. The IBC 2024 conference website can be found [here](#).

Aims of WikiProject IBC 2024

In subsequent meetings, the four collaborators decided on the four main aims of this WikiProject. It was decided that the main priority was to offer an in-person Wikidata workshop to botanists attending IBC 2024 and to ensure that this workshop was open to both the English and Spanish speaking conference attendees.

We also aimed to advocate the use of Wikidata at IBC 2024 both formally, through presentations and posters, as well as informally, by undertaking outreach with Congress participants.

Finally, because the Congress was such a massive gathering of botanists from all over the world, we saw this as an opportunity to increase the quality of botanist items in Wikidata. We therefore aimed to “Wikify” IBC 2024 by improving participant related Wikidata items and by undertaking photography at IBC 2024 that would be uploaded into Wikimedia Commons.

Collaboration

Zoom Meeting

[Wikidata WikiProject organisers meeting on Zoom](#) by Heidi Meudt, [CC BY 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Collaboration methods

We organised our project by holding regular Zoom meetings in the lead up to IBC 2024 and worked together on Google docs and sheets. All of these tools allowed us to collaborate across time zones which was important given that the organisers of this project were based in New Zealand, Germany and Portugal.

From November 2023 to July 2024, we met fortnightly - and then, from the beginning of May, weekly - to contribute to our WikiProject and prepare resources for the Congress. After our return from the Congress, from 12 September 2024, we aimed to meet weekly to produce a scholarly article for the scientific journal *Annals of Botany* on the benefits to the botany community when engaging with Wikidata (see below under “Unanticipated advantages of agile attitude”).

Google docs and sheets, e-mail, and a WhatsApp group were all used to keep us up to date on progress and empowered us to discuss issues raised outside the Zoom meetings, thus avoiding time zones detrimentally affecting communications.

Collaboration with three Wikimedia country chapters - Spain, Germany and New Zealand

[Wikidata Workshop IBC2024 giveaways](#) by S.v.Mering, [CC BY 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

We met several times with Wikimedia España, to explain our project and to help raise awareness amongst the Spanish editing community about our outreach efforts. Wikimedia España was extremely supportive of our efforts, paying for Wikidata editor and academic [Tomás Saorín Pérez](#) to attend IBC 2024 so he could attend the workshop and provide critical bilingual support. Wikimania España also provided us with swag giveaways for attendees of the workshop.

The Wikidata portion of Wikimedia Deutschland also supplied swag giveaways which we provided both to workshop attendees as well as conference attendees who interacted with our Wikidata poster.

Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand (WANZ), including both the leadership committee as well as the wider New Zealand Wiki editing community, were also very supportive of our efforts. The WANZ committee approved funding for what turned out to be one of the most impactful pieces of outreach material. The bookmarks (an image of which can be found on page 16) were particularly helpful as they contained a QR code that directed IBC 2024 attendees to our WikiProject page as well as url links to both the WikiProject Wikidata page and the IBC 2024 Wikidata poster.

The bookmark was helpful as we ensured our WikiProject page had an image of our IBC Wikidata poster on the home tab as well as our contact details. There was also a Resources tab that gave a collation of the “how to edit” materials used in the IBC workshop. This ensured we were able to hand over the bookmark to any Congress attendee who was interested in the Wikidata poster, who wanted to contact us or who expressed an interest in learning how to edit Wikidata.

WikiProject page creation

Wikidata:WikiProject IBC 2024

Home IBC Workshop Resources Meetings Outcomes

WikiProject International Botanical Congress 2024

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- 3 Organisers
- 4 Wikidata Workshop
- 5 Funding and support acknowledgements

About Wikidata WikiProject International Botanical Congress 2024 [edit]

The International Botanical Congress [?] (IBC) takes place once every six years. The organisers of this WikiProject see this conference as an ideal opportunity to engage with the wider botanical community, educate them about the potential of Wikidata and to train them in its use. We will also use this opportunity to improve the data held in Wikidata about the participants, presenters and their contributions to botany.

Aims and scope [edit]

- Deliver a Wikidata workshop to 50 conference participants
- Deliver Wikidata related presentations and poster at the conference (2 paper and 2 posters have been accepted)
- Engage in informal outreach during the conference
- "Wikify" the conference, its participants and their contributions to botany

Organisers [edit] [subscribe]

- [Ambrosia10](#) (talk) 03:16, 25 January 2024 (UTC) [reply]
- [Stitchbird2](#) (talk) 07:56, 25 January 2024 (UTC) [reply]
- [S.v.Mering](#) (talk) 09:54, 25 January 2024 (UTC) [reply]
- [Joaquimsantos1978](#) (talk) 15:54, 25 January 2024 (UTC) [reply]

[Screenshot of the Wikidata WikiProject IBC 2024 project page](#). Wikimedia Foundation, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#) via Wikimedia Commons.

The [WikiProject page](#) was created in order to assist with the organisation of the WikiProject and to aid in advertising and outreach as well as to keep the wider Wiki community up to date on project progress.

Presentation Abstract

The organising group submitted a conference presentation abstract titled [Engaging with Wikidata: Benefits and impacts for botanists and institutions](#). Unfortunately, and much to the surprise of our group, this abstract was rejected as an oral presentation by the Congress organising committee. This indicated to us that the organising committee was unaware of the growing use of Wikidata by the international botanical community. However, we were invited to create a poster. This turned out to be a blessing in disguise (see below under “Unanticipated advantages of agile attitude”).

We were relieved to discover that the [abstract on the Women Genera project](#) was selected as an oral presentation by the organising committee of the Congress. This selection reassured us that Wikidata still had a presence during presentations at the conference portion of IBC 2024.

Virtual onboarding workshop, 9 July 2024

The organising group recognised that continuing engagement with Wikidata by new Wiki editors is increased when those new editors are exposed to multiple learning opportunities. We also recognised that some Congress participants may have conflicting responsibilities and may not be able to attend the in person IBC Wikidata workshop. We therefore decided to offer a virtual onboarding workshop in the weeks leading up to the Congress in July 2024.

We had originally intended to obtain the email addresses of those who registered for the in person workshop and then to reach out to those attendees directly, informing them of this online opportunity to start engaging with Wikidata. However, as a result of the delay by Congress organisers in creating a registration page for all conference workshops (including ours), we decided to offer this session to anyone interested in learning about Wikidata.

We advertised the onboarding workshop via social media and email. We also placed information about the event on our WikiProject page. We set up a Zoom meeting and required attendees to register. This meant we had participant emails, empowering us to contact them directly, and could also avoid anyone spamming our Zoom meeting. Prior to the online workshop we sent out a reminder email to all those who had registered. This email included links to information on how to get a Wikidata account and resources on how to edit Wikidata.

This onboarding event took place on Tuesday, 9 July 2024 and was very successful with over 65 people registering from 17 countries. On the day, we had 40 participants from 11 countries attending. As we aimed this presentation at an international audience, we recognised time zones would play a part in hindering attendees attending on the day.

To overcome this, we recorded the presentation and added it to [Youtube](#). As at the writing of this report, this video had been viewed 92 times. We then emailed this recording as well as the link to the presentation slides to all those who registered.

To aid sharing and reuse we also added the [recording and workshop slides to Zenodo](#) under a Creative Commons Attribution licence. As at the writing of this report these Zenodo links have been viewed over 2000 times and downloaded 150 times. We also uploaded the [video](#) and [slides](#) to Wikimedia Commons.

Screenshot of the onboarding and introduction virtual workshop slides in Wikimedia Commons. Wikimedia Foundation, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

We asked online participants to fill out a survey so we had an opportunity to improve our upcoming in person workshops based on their feedback. We received 14 completed surveys, and had several participants reach out to us giving very positive feedback about the virtual onboarding session. This feedback included a post by a New Zealand botanist Bec Stanley which can be viewed [on LinkedIn](#).

Survey results

As explained, 14 of the participants filled in our survey after the virtual onboarding event. The following are screenshots giving some of the anonymised results from that survey. All images are licensed by the authors of this report for reuse under a [CC BY 4.0](#) licence.

In summary, the survey showed that attendees were overall very satisfied with the event, and found it to be relevant or very relevant for themselves, their job and their institution. Attendees said they were likely to continue editing, contributing and upskilling in Wikidata in future.

How satisfied were you with the event?

15 responses

How relevant is Wikidata for your

How likely are you to edit Wikidata in the future?

14 responses

Are you interested in joining a local Wikimedia community?

 Copy

14 responses

- Yes
- No
- Maybe
- Don't know/Prefer not to answer

Would you like to attend more Wikidata workshops?

 Copy

14 responses

- Yes
- No
- Maybe
- Don't know/Prefer not to answer

In-person multilingual Wikidata workshop, 21 July 2024

[Attendees of the Wikidata WikiProject IBC 2024 in person workshop](#) by Siobhan Leachman, [CC0](#) via Wikimedia Commons.

The in-person workshop was held on Sunday, 21 July 2024, about two weeks after the virtual onboarding session, during the weekend between the first portion of IBC 2024 (nomenclature week, 15-19 July) and the second portion (conference week, 21-27 July). It was a very successful event with 22 participants from multiple countries editing in multiple languages including participants from the Global South and the African continent. We were thrilled that just under half of the participants were from Latin America, and about half of the attendees were also female.

We successfully helped participants to create an account and trained them on creating Wikidata items for people, publications and taxa. We also explained how to query Wikidata and gave biodiversity examples of reuse of Wikidata QIDs as well as the data contained in Wikidata.

Although there were 22 attendees of the workshop only 14 signed up to the [event dashboard](#). This was a learning opportunity for the organisers. We found it challenging to give a presentation to the attendees and then troubleshoot and train participants while at the same time undertaking administrative tasks such as ensuring attendees had signed up to the event dashboard. In future, should this effort be replicated, we suggest organisers allocate to one person the administrative tasks to be undertaken during the workshop with the other

organisers undertaking the one to one or one to group mentoring during the editing sessions of the workshop.

Another challenge organisers were faced with during the editing portion of the Wikidata workshop was that many participants initially created Wikidata items for themselves. This behaviour was unanticipated as a lot of effort had gone into creating resources giving participants lists of people in need of Wikidata items.

Although the creation of your own Wikidata item is not as frowned upon amongst the Wikidata community as it is for people creating their own Wikipedia article in the Wikipedia community, this behaviour by participants educated the organisers to deal with this type of editing and to emphasise conflict of interest issues more specifically during presentations at the beginning of events.

Resources for multilingual Wikidata workshop

One of the major benefits of organising this workshop were the resources discovered and created for it. The Vanderbilt University website [LearnWikidata.net](https://learn.wikidata.net) was perfect for our needs. This website provides short introductory videos teaching information professionals about Wikidata. These videos are available in multiple languages including English and Spanish, making it extremely useful for our project.

We also reused Wikidata training resources created during yet another Wikidata adjacent collaboration Siobhan had been involved in - [the Hidden Figures project](#). This project is producing a multi module CURE - a Course-based Undergraduate Research Experience. As part of this project, CURE creators produced Wikidata “how to” training documentation for a teaching module aimed at undergraduate biology students. Although these “how to” documents had yet to be published on the [QUBES website](#) at the time of the Wikidata workshop, the drafts were published in Zenodo and openly licensed, and so we were able to reuse and adapt them for the Wikidata workshop.

As we were aiming to support Spanish speaking botanists during the Wikidata workshop, we prioritised the translation of these English language training resources into Spanish. This work was undertaken by Heidi and her husband [Mauricio López Langenbach](#), with Wikidata editors from Wikimedia España also checking the translation.

We also created two resources to provide workshop participants with names of people (botanists) that could be worked on during the workshop. First, Joaquim prepared a [Google spreadsheet](#) giving a list of about 550 mostly historical botanical collectors from the [Willkomm Herbarium](#) at the University of Coimbra. Many of these botanical collectors were from the Iberian Peninsula or undertook collecting work around the Iberian Peninsula or in South America. Thus this spreadsheet assisted participants in working on resources that were both relevant to our workshop but also helped address a geographical bias on Wikidata.

Second, Heidi and Siobhan created a [Google spreadsheet](#) of over 1600 participants at the Congress, by downloading information on organisers and speakers from the IBC 2024 website. These botanists are actively performing botanical research throughout the world, and include many from Spain and South America, as well as other areas of the Global South. This spreadsheet not only assisted the efforts of the organisers to “Wikify” the conference it also provided a list of contemporary botanists in need of Wikidata items.

Proactive sharing of Wikidata workshop resources

The screenshot displays the Zenodo interface for the 'IBC Wikidata' community repository. At the top, there's a search bar and navigation links. A 'Planned intervention' notice is visible. The main content area shows search results for 'IBC Wikidata', with 10 results found. The results are sorted by 'Newest'. Three items are visible:

- Final follow-up workshop: Upskilling in Wikidata for maximum impact** (August 28, 2024): A presentation by Leachman, Siobhan; Meudt, Heidi; von Mering, Sabine; and 1 other. Description: Slides of a virtual Wikidata workshop given on the 28th of August 2024. A final follow-up event after a full in person workshop held at the International Botanical Congress 2024 in Madrid on the 21st of July 2024. Part of IBC Wikidata. Uploaded on August 28, 2024. 33 views, 13 downloads.
- In-person workshop Upskilling in Wikidata for maximum impact IBC 2024** (August 23, 2024): A presentation by Leachman, S.; Meudt, Heidi; von Mering, Sabine; and 1 other. Description: Slides of full in person workshop held at the International Botanical Congress 2024 in Madrid on the 21st of July 2024. A related virtual onboarding and introductory Wikidata workshop was also given on the 9th of July 2024. Link to slides in Google docs. Part of IBC Wikidata. Uploaded on August 23, 2024. 30 views, 11 downloads.
- WikiProject International Botanical Congress 2024** (August 7, 2024): A presentation by Leachman, Siobhan; von Mering, Sabine; Meudt, Heidi; and 1 other. Description: Presentation slides and script for Siobhan Leachman and Heidi Meudt's presentation on the WikiProject International Botanical Congress at Wikimania 2024. A recording of this presentation can be found on Youtube. Part of IBC Wikidata. Uploaded on August 7, 2024. 43 views, 34 downloads.

Screenshot of the IBC Wikidata community repository on Zenodo. [Zenodo](#). [CC BY 4.0](#)

We were extremely keen to ensure the resources produced and used for the Wikidata workshop could be easily reused by the wider biodiversity and Wiki communities. To this end we added both the English and Spanish versions of the Wikidata training resources to [Zenodo](#). Zenodo is a research repository that provides each of those documents with a DOI or digital object identifier. DOIs made it easier to find and also share these resources on other platforms, including Wikidata.

In order to collate and ensure all the WikiProject resources were easily found within Zenodo, Joaquim created an IBC Wikidata community on Zenodo. This community and all our associated Zenodo publications, including the English and Spanish version of the Wikidata training resources, can be found at [this link](#).

We also added the [English](#) and [Spanish](#) how-to training documents to Wikimedia Commons and then ensured that the Wikimedia Commons file was added to the Wikidata items created for those publications. For the Wikidata items and their associated publications uploaded into Wikimedia Commons, see [Q125662449](#) and [Q127467987](#).

We shared the links to these resources on social media, on the [GLAMwiki](#) and the Wikidata newsletters, at Wiki meetups, at meetings with Wikimedia España as well as on Telegram with the Wikidata WikiProject Biodiversity and the Wikidata groups.

IBC 2024 Wikidata Poster

Engaging with Wikidata

Benefits and impacts for botanists and institutions

Sabine von Mering¹, Siobhan Leachman², Joaquim Santos³, Heidi M. Meudt⁴

¹Museum für Naturkunde - Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science, Berlin, Germany, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2982-7792>

²Independent researcher, Wellington, New Zealand, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5398-7721>

³Centre for Functional Ecology, Dept. of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2160-4968>

⁴Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa, Wellington, New Zealand, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2433-9071>

Scan to see our poster on your device

Fig. 1. Visualisation of one of Ynes Mexia's research expeditions based on Wikidata items, ODbL.

Scan to see a visualisation of this expedition --

Wikidata is an important tool for botanists.

Fig. 3. Botanist Ynes Mexia (1870-1938), NPS Photo, Public domain.

- Wikidata is a multilingual linked open knowledge base to which anyone can contribute.
- It contains CC0 licensed data and empowers the referencing of this data thus showing the source of this information.
- Wikidata can help disambiguate and enrich data on botanists and collectors of botanical specimens.

Wikidata items on plant taxa contain data from multiple sources, with references.

Fig. 4A. Wikidata item for the plant species Mexianthus mexicanus, CC BY-SA 4.0

- Sources can include links to the original description of the taxon
- Wikidata may also have items for alternative names for a plant species and can link synonyms to their publications.
- An image of the species can also be added (Fig. 4A).

Wikidata can illuminate connections of botanical research expeditions.

- Research expeditions are a major source of objects contained in natural history institutions (Fig. 1).
- Currently there is no single database that contains comprehensive data on the world's scientific expeditions.
- Natural history institutions are using Wikidata to help link historical and contemporary research expeditions to other entities such as participants, locations, publications, and institutions (Fig. 2).
- These links are being made within Wikidata as well as in collection management systems and catalogues.

Fig. 4. Scholia topic visualization for botanist Ynes Mexia, CC BY-SA 4.0.

Information in Wikidata can be queried & visualised.

- The Wikidata identifier for a botanist can be used in Scholia to generate a topic visualisation graph (Fig. 4).
- The website Bionomia uses a botanist's Wikidata identifier or ORCID to create a profile linking them to specimens, dates, taxa, and institutions (Fig. 5).

Fig. 2. Scholia topic visualization graph for the Mexia Mexico Expedition 1926-1927, CC BY-SA 4.0.

Fig. 5. Bionomia profile for botanist Ynes Mexia, with permission.

Wikidata acts as a database hub and a universal identifier.

Fig. 4B. Wikidata item for the species Mexianthus mexicanus showing links to other identifiers, CC BY-SA 4.0

- Wikidata links to identifiers such as the Catalogue of Life, GBIF, IPNI, POWO, and Tropicos, among others (Fig. 4B).
- Wikidata can facilitate access to information in different source databases from natural history institutions, herbaria and data aggregators.

Scan to see more information and practical resources on our WikiProject IBC 2024 page

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Engaging with Wikidata IBC Poster by Sabine von Mering, Siobhan Leachman, Joaquim Santos and Heidi Meudt., [CC BY 4.0](#). Also on [Wikimedia Commons](#).

As explained previously, one major disappointment during this WikiProject was that our abstract on how the Wikidata can benefit the botanical community was rejected as an oral presentation by the Congress organising committee. However, we were invited to create a poster.

We decided to submit a physical poster instead of an electronic poster to ensure we would have a physical presence at a designated area at the conference to undertake our outreach. We wanted to maximise the impact of this poster so we licensed it under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 licence](#).

Even though we chose the “physical” poster option, we also created digital versions of it to increase its reach with conference attendees and also with the wider botanical and Wiki communities, before, during and after the conference. First, we uploaded it into [Zenodo](#), which created a DOI. This helped us link to the poster and also ensured we could share the poster on multiple platforms. At the writing of this report, Zenodo reports our poster has had 433 views and 174 downloads.

Along with the DOI, we also created a QR code for the poster. This created an electronic version and provided yet another avenue to access this resource as we printed the QR on the poster itself. Conference attendees could then scan the QR code to see the electronic version of the poster. Finally, we uploaded the poster into [Wikimedia Commons](#) and then actively shared it on social media prior to the conference to generate interest.

We used the poster as advertising to increase both awareness of and attendance at both the online and in-person Wikidata workshops.

We also made sure to upload other visualisations and slides created for our workshops into Wikimedia Commons as well as any images we took during the Congress; see this [Wikimedia Commons category](#). We wanted to ensure the Wiki community could take full advantage of our work now and into the future.

Wikifying the IBC 2024 conference

As explained previously another priority of this WikiProject was to wikify the Congress. We aimed to document this important event and use Wikidata to increase the profile of the organisers, scientific advisors and presenters of the Congress. We started the process of wikifying IBC 2024 in January 2024.

Our wikifying workflow was first to ensure the IBC 2024 conference presenter had a Wikidata item. If there were duplicate items we merged those. We then enriched their item. We prioritised adding their occupation, education and/or employer. We also researched their identifiers. We were particularly keen to add their ORCID, VIAF and other library identifiers, including the Biodiversity Heritage Library creator identifier. We then added botany specific identifiers to their Wikidata item.

Finally we put the person through the [Author Disambiguator tool](#) to connect their Wikidata item to their scholarly output. We added a link to their [Scholia](#) profile to the spreadsheet. We did this to make it easier to find this information should we need it when we personally met the actual botanists we had been wikifying at the Congress in Madrid.

This wikification of the conference suffered project creep when the WikiProject organisers eventually decided to cover all 1600+ botanists who were the presenting authors of an oral presentation at the conference as listed by the [IBC 2024 Congress website](#). This has resulted in this wikification effort, as at the writing of this report, still being ongoing. As at September 2024, we have created or significantly improved Wikidata items for 587 IBC 2024 botanists. The aim of the organisers of the Wikidata WikiProject IBC 2024 is to complete this work over the next 6 months and then upload the [Google sheets spreadsheet](#) into Zenodo, generate a DOI and empower the more active sharing of this dataset.

This wikification work can also be tracked via a Wikidata query on the [People on focus list of WikiProject IBC 2024](#).

[Slide 17 of the Wikimania 2024 presentation WikiProject International Congress 2024](#) by Siobhan Leachman, Sabine von Mering, Heidi Meudt and Joaquim Santos [CC BY 4.0](#) via Wikimedia Commons.

The visualisation above gives an indication of the impact of this work. This is a visualisation of a Scholia coauthor graph for a botanist presenting at IBC 2024 both before and after disambiguation work. As you can see, our wikifying work has not only enriched this presenter's Wikidata item, it has also linked this botanist to multiple collaborators.

Our efforts in the lead up and during IBC 2024 to wikify the conference gained coverage in a [German blog](#) which outlined how we went about openly documenting IBC 2024.

Informal outreach undertaken during the Congress, 21-27 July 2024

As previously explained we also undertook informal outreach. We talked to people during coffee breaks, lunches and dinners out. We talked “Wiki Wiki Wiki”. Having a physical poster assisted us as it gave us a gathering point to discuss Wikidata with conference participants. We were extremely lucky as our poster was situated very close to where Congress participants obtained coffee, and was also near the exhibition area where scientific journals, botanical societies, and other groups had their exhibit stalls. This facilitated a greater number of engagement opportunities than might otherwise be the case if the poster had been situated further away from where attendees gathered.

Bookmarks were also created for the event, thanks to funding from [Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand](#). These massively aided our outreach efforts. We handed these out to participants during the workshop as well as during the Congress. We also placed them near our poster, providing those interested with links not just to the poster but also our IBC WikiProject.

[WikiProject IBC 2024 bookmarks](#) by Heidi Meudt, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Wikidata for Botanists follow-up workshop, 28 August 2024

The organisers of the WikiProject decided to hold a follow-up workshop after returning to our respective countries from the Congress. The aim of this online follow-up workshop was to share with both the virtual and the in-person workshop attendees the progress made in their events, to provide again access to the “how to” documentation, and to create an opportunity for attendees to share their editing stories, raise issues or problems they had with editing, and discuss their thoughts with the rest of the group.

The slides and script for this online follow-up workshop presentation were uploaded into [Zenodo](#) and the slide deck was also uploaded into [Wikimedia Commons](#).

Unlike the previous onboarding virtual workshop we deliberately decided not to record this follow up workshop. We wanted the attendees to feel comfortable admitting errors and asking questions and decided that recording such would make new editors reluctant to share their challenges.

This workshop was held on Wednesday, 28 August 2024, lasted an hour and was successful in giving participants an opportunity to discuss any editing issues they might have. Fourteen people from 11 countries signed up for this final workshop in the series, with 9 attending from 8 different countries.

Communication with the Wiki community

NEW ZEALAND REPORT

WikiProject International Botanical Congress 2024, a presentation to the Natural History Museum, London & Kew Gardens staff and a Research expeditions edit-a-thon

By [Ambrosia10](#) & [Avocadobabygirl](#)

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WikiProject IBC 2024

Recently two New Zealand editors [Ambrosia10](#) and [Stitchbird2](#), as well as their two Wikidata WikiProject collaborators [S.v.Mering](#) and [JoaquimSantos78](#), attended the International Botanical Congress in Madrid. The group successfully delivered a Wikidata workshop at the Congress to 22 new and emerging Wikidata editors, presented a Wikidata related presentation on a research into women after who flowering plant genera have been named and presented a poster on the benefits to botanists in engaging more with Wikidata.

This poster generated much interest during the conference and led to two editors of the prestigious botany journal the Annals of Botany inviting the group to submit a paper on the benefits of Wikidata to that journal. A digital copy of the Wikidata poster has been uploaded into Wikimedia Commons and can be found at [this link](#).

The informal engagement efforts by the Wikidata WikiProject IBC organisers were assisted by bookmarks created by the ground and funded by Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand. Organisers were able to hand out the bookmarks which contained a QR code to the project page which contained a copy of not only the Wikidata poster but also contained links to help interested attendees begin their Wikidata editing journey.

During the run up to the Congress the organisers of the project attempted to “wikify” the conference with their efforts covered by a [German publication](#). While at the Congress these efforts continued with the organisers taking photos of notable botanists and creating and enriching Wikidata items for the same.

Screenshot of the [New Zealand report portion of the July GLAMwiki newsletter](#) showing the updates given to the wider Wiki community by organisers of the Wikidata WikiProject IBC 2024. Wikimedia Foundation, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#).

We wanted to keep the Wiki community up to date on our efforts. As well as creating a WikiProject page, outlined in the WikiProject page creation section above, we also reached out to and set up several meetings with Wikimedia España. Our aim was to let them know of our efforts and explain why we were undertaking this outreach. Sabine also had meetings with Wikimedia Deutschland and a German blog post about the IBC project activities is in preparation.

We created multiple posts on the WikiProject in the GLAMwiki newsletter (see the [June](#), [July](#) and [August 2024](#) newsletters). We reported on our progress to the Aotearoa New Zealand and Wellington meetups. Finally we submitted an abstract to [Wikimania 2024](#) to update the wider community on our IBC 2024 WikiProject. This was accepted by the organising committee. The [presentation video](#) on the WikiProject given at Wikimania 2024 can be found on Wikimedia Commons and the [slide deck and script](#) can be found on Zenodo.

Because Wikimania 2024 was held in Katowice, Poland from 6-10 August 2024, about a week after IBC 2024 finished, three of the organisers of this WikiProject (Siobhan, Sabine and Heidi) were able to attend both conferences as part of the same larger trip. This was particularly important for Siobhan and Heidi, who had travelled a very long distance from New Zealand. The timing was fortuitous and meant they could attend two international conferences with only one set of return flights, significantly decreasing both the costs and carbon footprint of their travel while doubling the outreach and outputs.

Importantly, attendance at Wikimania 2024 allowed us to come full circle by sharing the benefits of the Wikiverse with the botanical community (starting with IBC 2024), and sharing the benefits of working with the botanical community with the Wiki community (starting with Wikimania 2024).

WikiProject IBC 2024 venn diagram by Heidi Meudt, [CC BY 4.0](#)

Main challenges with the WikiProject

As explained previously, we faced a major challenge when the abstract for a presentation on Wikidata to the conference portion of the Congress was rejected as an oral presentation. We had to pivot to creating a poster. We were aware that conference posters often do not have the same impact as a conference presentation.

We therefore prioritised the sharing and reuse of the poster created, before, during and after the Congress. We wanted to ensure the poster's impact was as great as, if not greater, than a presentation at IBC 2024.

Another major challenge was that the Congress organisers seemed overwhelmed. There were severe delays in having all workshops added to the IBC 2024 website, in obtaining a workshop registration page and obtaining information on the location of where the workshop would be held. There was also little advertising of workshops provided by the Congress organisers. This was a major issue for us as it significantly hindered the recruiting of attendees.

We attempted to sidestep the impact of these organisational delays by placing information about the workshop on our WikiProject page, actively informing Congress attendees via social media and email that the workshop was being organised, and proactively emailing multiple botany organisations as well as possibly interested botanical colleagues, informing them of the workshop. Although we were delighted to have 22 attendees attend our in-person workshop, we had actually planned for and could have accommodated twice that many.

Funding of the WikiProject

Another major challenge was the difficulty we had in obtaining funding for this initiative. The lack of funding almost derailed the WikiProject before it was established. First we attempted to ask Wikidata and Wikimedia Deutschland to fund this initiative. Unfortunately we were told that Wikimedia Deutschland did not fund initiatives outside of Germany. This is despite Wikidata being an international project.

We then attempted to apply for a Wikimedia Foundation rapid grant. Unfortunately we were immediately rejected. We were told rapid grants do not fund initiatives related to conferences.

As this WikiProject was internationally focused, individuals in our group did not feel it was appropriate to apply to their Wikimedia country chapters for funding. For example, Siobhan was reluctant to apply to Aotearoa New Zealand for funding as she would need to show the benefit to New Zealand for this initiative. This would have been difficult as this project was very much an international project.

All of this was extremely frustrating to the WikiProject organisers as our project seemed to be slipping through the funding cracks. As a result, Siobhan reached out to R. Yael Weissburg, the vice president of Community Growth and Movement Building at the Wikimedia Foundation. We wanted to draw her attention to what we regarded as a community-wide funding issue for those Wikimedians undertaking outreach work with international communities based around a theme rather than based around a country.

Weissburg facilitated members of the Wikidata WikiProject IBC 2024 in making an application directly to the Wikimedia Foundation, and we were very fortunate and extremely grateful to receive a grant that empowered us to undertake this project.

Support from Wikimedia country chapters

Despite not gaining specific project funding from country chapters, multiple Wikimedia country chapters definitely provided us with support in different ways. Wikimedia España in particular was extremely supportive of our efforts. They connected us with Tomás Saorin Pérez, a Spanish academic and Wikimedian experienced in Wikidata, and funded him to personally attend and assist with the workshop. Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand provided funding for us to produce bookmarks promoting our project. Wikidata swag giveaways were also provided by Wikimedia Deutschland, which again assisted with our outreach efforts.

Solutions to challenges

The organisers of the Wikidata WikiProject IBC 2024 wish to emphasise that when undertaking projects like this, organisers need to remain agile in the face of adversity. If your abstract gets rejected, create a poster. If the conference organisation is not optimal, find workarounds to promote, advertise and plan for your events. We held a virtual onboarding event, emailed information to botanical organisations, advertised on social media, and asked multiple botanists to share those posts on their social media accounts as well as with organisations and colleagues that might be interested. We made sure to update and link to our WikiProject page, providing an alternative platform to the official conference website. WikiProject organisers can and should be creative and resourceful, working together to find solutions to challenges.

Unanticipated advantages of agile attitude

[Wikidata poster annals of botany card](#) by S.v.Mering, [CC BY 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

There were unanticipated advantages gained as a result of us remaining agile in the face of adversity. Our poster was extremely successful. Not only did it attract the attention of multiple attendees of the conference, it also attracted the attention of two editors of the scientific journal, [Annals of Botany](#). This is a very prestigious botany journal. As a result of our poster, we were invited to publish in that journal an article on Wikidata and why it is important for botanists and their institutions.

This success has resulted in the Wikidata WikiProject IBC 2024 being extended for at least another 6 months to enable organisers to create and submit this scholarly publication by early 2025. This invitation to submit a paper is a very exciting and satisfying outcome as a result of all of our hard work and efforts with the WikiProject IBC 2024 to date, and is a massive opportunity to increase the knowledge, understanding, use and editing of Wikidata by the botanical community.

Replicating this WikiProject in 2029

[Leucospermum conocarpodendron subsp. viridum](#) at Wynberg Park Cape Town by Andrew Massyn, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons

We are aware that the next [International Botanical Congress](#) will be held in 2029 in Cape Town, South Africa.

We plan to reach out to [Wikimedia South Africa](#) to alert them of this opportunity to engage proactively with not just the organising committee of IBC 2029 but also with the presenters and participants of that Congress, given the high probability that many will be from the African continent.

We intend to share this report with Wikimedia South Africa and to offer to assist them to follow in the footsteps of this WikiProject to continue to engage with the international botanical community. Given that Wikimania 2025 will also be in Africa (Nairobi, Kenya), there is also an opportunity to connect with other Wikipedia country chapters in Africa prior to 2029. We would love to build on the momentum we have created with WikiProject IBC 2024, and continue to advocate for the upskilling and training of botanists in the Wikiverse.

The importance of funding themed WikiProjects

The writers of this report wish to emphasise how important this and similar WikiProjects are for undertaking outreach with academic or scientific communities. WikiProjects that aim to engage with particular academic communities, be it botanists, architects, geologists, historians, etc., at events where they gather - for example at conferences, universities, museums, libraries and other institutions - are extremely important. We believe it is clear from the outcomes of this project that it is a worthwhile investment of grant funds and therefore encourage the Wikimedia Foundation to facilitate this happening.

Thank you

The organisers each feel it has been a privilege to work with this group of amazing Wiki contributors. To have the opportunity to reach out to the botanical community has been an honour. We wish to express our gratitude to the Wikimedia Foundation for the financial support, to our home country Wikimedia Chapters, to Wikimedia España, and to the employers and our families that supported our attendance at the XX International Botanical Congress and later, Wikimania 2024. These were unforgettable experiences that have positively impacted the Wiki community, the botanical community, and each of us personally. We feel that the Wikiverse has been made better because of it.